

CORRELATION BETWEEN RISK FACTORS AND CLINICOPATHOLOGY OF COLORECTAL CANCER: AN OBSERVATIONAL COHORT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Colorectal cancer (CRC) remains a major health concern globally, with increasing incidence and mortality rates. This observational cohort study was conducted at King George Hospital, Visakhapatnam, focusing on non-modifiable risk factors associated with CRC among 182 patients diagnosed with advanced-stage disease from February 2017 to August 2020. Inclusion criteria were patients aged 18 or older with confirmed advanced CRC, while those with incomplete medical records or secondary cancers were excluded. Results revealed a higher CRC prevalence in men (60.43%) compared to women (39.56%), with the majority of cases occurring in the 51-60 age group. Smoking emerged as a significant risk factor, predominantly affecting men and correlating with an increased incidence of right-sided colon tumors. Obesity, as measured by BMI, was associated with an elevated risk of CRC across both genders, with a notable prevalence in the same age group. Alcohol consumption did not show a statistically significant correlation with CRC risk. Tumor differentiation patterns varied, with well-differentiated tumors more common in the 51-60 age group. This study underscores the relevance of age, gender, and lifestyle factors in CRC risk, advocating for targeted preventive strategies and tailored therapeutic approaches to address these non-modifiable risk factors.

INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the highly frequent cancers worldwide (Kanna S., 2012). CRC is the 3rd most common cancer in men and the second most common cancer in women. CRC is a multifactorial disease linked to lifestyle, genetic and environmental factors. Although there are hereditary and non-hereditary CRC types, the majority are non-hereditary and commonly caused by somatic mutations in response to environmental factors (Ferlay J., 2013). In the past few years, scientists have concentrated their thoughtfulness on the mechanisms behind these factors and the methods of enhancing disease prevention and treatment. CRC is not a homogenous disease but can be classified into different subtypes, which are characterized by specific

molecular and morphological alterations. Although outcomes of CRC have improved, it is clear that from a genomic standpoint CRC is not one disease, but a heterogeneous group of malignancies that arise within one organ. This means that different subtypes have different outcomes; the ability to subtype tumors in the clinic would be highly favorable, enabling optimal treatment for individual patients (Aran V., 2016). In India, the annual incidence rates (AARs) for colon cancer and rectal cancer in men are 4.4 and 4.1 per 100000, respectively. The AAR for colon cancer in women is 3.9 per 100000. Colon cancer ranks 8th and rectal cancer ranks 9th among men. For women, rectal cancer does not figure in the top 10 cancers, whereas colon cancer ranks 9th (NCRP., 2013).

All new cases should be discussed at the tumor board or at multidisciplinary team (MDT) meetings and the treatment strategy should be confirmed. In a majority of patients with localized disease, resection will be the treatment of choice, with consideration given to adjuvant chemotherapy following resection. Occasionally, patients will present with a local disease that has infiltrated adjacent structures; in these cases, the use of preoperative chemotherapy should be considered. Most patients with metastatic disease will be considered for palliative chemotherapy. A small proportion of these patients may be curable.

Over the past decade, a number of clinical trials have shown a significant survival benefit for adjuvant chemotherapy with 5-fluorouracil (5-FU), capecitabine, and FOLFOX chemotherapy after resection of stage III colorectal tumours. Capecitabine has been demonstrated to be at least as effective as bolus 5-FU/ folinic acid (FA) in the adjuvant setting (X-ACT trial)³². The MOSAIC trial demonstrated that adjuvant chemotherapy increases the 5-year survival rate to 73% for stage III/Dukes C tumors treated with adjuvant FOLFOX compared to approximately 69% for tumors treated with 5-FU/FA³³. The benefit of adjuvant chemotherapy for stage II/Dukes B tumors is controversial, as trials have not consistently demonstrated significant advantages with regard to overall survival and disease-free survival³³. The absolute improvement in overall survival at 5 years with adjuvant 5-FU-based chemotherapy is approximately 3–4%, although the benefit may be higher in those with high-risk features (Harris DJ., 2009).

METHODS

Patients:

The required data was obtained from the medical records databases that were searched to retrieve the records of patients who were diagnosed with advanced colorectal cancer with local progression or distant metastasis and who underwent first-line systemic chemotherapy for advanced colorectal cancer between February 1, 2017, and August 31, 2020.

The records were analyzed for information on demographics, clinical and pathological variables including anatomical distribution, clinical presentations, tumor stage based on the TNM, histological type, grade of tumor, date of diagnosis, duration of clinical features, tumor location, the type of surgery performed, endoscopy findings, laboratory findings, histological findings, and surgical notes were extracted. The treatment type including chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and follow-ups were also analyzed. If the data is not available according to the study designs was obtained using telephonic conversations.

Study Duration March 2019 to February 2022.

Patients were interviewed using a semi-structured pre-designed questionnaire with sections eliciting information on personal, demographic, clinical, lab reports, etc. Information was sought from the patient or his attendant/ relative.

Inclusion Criteria All patients with a provisional diagnosis of colorectal malignancies attending the Department of Oncology, Subjects who are between the age of 25-80 years.

Exclusion Criteria

The patients below 25 years and those with bleeding from the rectum due to benign polyps, benign ulcers, inflammatory bowel disease, diverticulosis, and subjects below the age of 25 years. The subjects who are diagnosed only with caecum abnormalities, splenic, and pancreatic abnormalities, pregnant women, breastfeeding women, and COVID-19-positive subjects were excluded from the study. Patients who had incomplete medical records or died from causes other than cancer were excluded from the study group.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were entered in an Excel spreadsheet for Windows and analyzed using GraphPad Prism 9. Data was distributed according to the parameters selected; Categorical variables were presented as percentages (%). The correlations of the selected factors were analyzed using multivariate analysis, correlation matrix with Pearson r correlation at 95% confidence interval and p-value was calculated using two-tailed. The considered p-value is at $p > 0.05$.

RESULTS

The study encompasses a diverse group of 182 colorectal subjects, with a focus on various subgroups. Among them, 160 are smokers, while 118 are undergoing chemotherapy, and 147 have an ostomy. This broad range of subjects allows for a comprehensive analysis of the impacts and interactions of smoking, chemotherapy, and ostomy on colorectal health.

Age versus Gender:

Table 1: Distribution of the study subjects by Age and Gender

Age/Gender	Male	Female	Total	% incidence (n=182)
20-30	6 (5.45)	2 (2.78)	8	4.40
31-40	12 (10.91)	6 (8.33)	18	9.89
41-50	28 (25.45)	13 (18.06)	41	22.53
51-60	36 (32.73)	36 (50.00)	72	39.56
61- 70	17 (15.45)	10 (13.89)	27	14.84
71-80	9 (8.18)	4 (5.56)	13	7.14
80	2 (1.82)	1 (1.39)	3	1.65
Total	110 (60.43%)	72 (39.56)	182	
*p-value	0.0001***	0.0001***	Pearson r correlation	
r value	0.9797	0.9791		

The incidence is more in men (60.43%) than in women (39.56%). The incidence of cancer was found to be more at the age of 51-60 years i.e 39.56% and the distribution is significant in men (32.73%) and women (50%) at the age of 51-60 years. There was a strong correlation between age and gender distributed a p-value of 0.0001.

Fig 1: Distribution of the study subjects by Age and Gender

Figure 2: Correlation of Age and Gender

XY data: Correlation of Age vs gender

This study indicated that the incidence is more in men than in women, it may be due to many protective factors in women, which men are related to hormonal differences, and it was observed more in the age group of 51-60 years.

Age versus year of registration:

Table 2: Distribution of the study subjects by Age and Year of registration

Age/Years	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	Total
20-30	4 (6.67)	0 (0)	4 (4.40)	8
31-40	6 (10.00)	2 (6.45)	10 (10.99)	18
41-50	14 (23.33)	6 (19.35)	21 (23.08)	41
51-60	23 (38.33)	16 (51.61)	33 (36.26)	72
61- 70	8 (13.33)	5 (16.13)	14 (15.38)	27
71-80	4 (6.67)	2 (6.45)	7 (7.69)	13
>80	1 (1.67)	0 (0)	2 (2.20)	3
Total	60(32.96%) (100)	31 (17.03) (100)	91(50%) (100)	182
*p-value	0.0001****	0.0001****	0.0001****	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.9959	0.9836	0.9973	

The distribution of the study subjects by age and year of registration which was 32.96% during 2019-20; 17.03% during 2020-21 and 50% during 2021-2022. The majority of the patients registered during 2021-2022. The age ranges 51-60 were found more compared to other age groups at all years i.e 38.33%, 51.61, and 36.26% in 2018-19; 2020-21, and 2021-22 respectively. There was a significant correlation between the age and year of registration at all the years at 0.0001p-value.

The number of registrations was found to be higher in 2021–2022 than in 2019–20 and 2020–2021. This may be due to the impact of COVID-19 on public health and reduced hospital attendance, so the number of registered cases is lower than in other years. As already said, the incidence of CRC is higher in 51-60 years and especially more in 2021-2022

Gender vs. year of diagnosis:

Table 3: Distribution of the study subjects by gender and Time of diagnosis

Time of diagnosis	Male	Female	Total
0-5yrs	18 (9.89)	16 (8.79)	34 (18.68)
6-10 yrs	60 (32.97)	26 (14.29)	86 (47.25)
≥11	32 (17.58)	30 (16.48)	62 (34.07)
Total	110 (60.43)	72 (39.56)	182
*p-value	0.1493 ^{ns}	0.4840 ^{ns}	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.9726	0.7247	

Colorectal cancer afflicts more males (60.43%) than females (39.56%). As is evident from Figure 4.2a, the number of male patients diagnosed with colorectal cancer outnumbers the female number. Among the total population, 47.25% patients are under 6-10 years of diagnosis. Our data shows that men have comparative risk of developing colorectal cancer than women. There was no correlation existed between the first time of diagnosis and age distribution according to Pearson r correlation.

Figure 3: Distribution of the study subjects by gender and Time of diagnosis

In this study, the first diagnosis was made 6-10 years after exposure to CRC in the selected population. For males, it was aged 6-10 years, and for females aged ≥ 11 years. Delayed diagnosis in women aged 51-60 years was associated with the premenopausal stage in women.

Gender vs BMI:

Table 4: Distribution of the study subjects by gender and BMI

BMI/Gender	Male	Female	Total
<25	13 (7.14)	18 (9.89)	31 (17.03)
25-29.9	72 (39.56)	33 (18.13)	105 (57.69)
≥ 30	25 (13.73)	21 (11.53)	46 (25.27)
Total	110	72	182 (100)
*p-value	0.0005***	0.0018**	Pearson r correlation
r value	1.000	1.000	

Obesity is majorly associated with colorectal cancer. The BMI was found to be more in males (39.56%) at 25-29.9 with 57.69%. A strong correlation is there between gender and BMI at p 0.0005 in men and 0.0018 in women.

Figure 5: Distribution of the study subjects by gender and BMI

The risk score increased progressively with overweight as estimated by body mass index (BMI), where the risk ranged from 1.79 for a BMI between 22 and 24 to 2.79 for a BMI over 30. In this study, most of the subjects are 25-29.9, among them more males than females were found. There was a strong significant association between gender and BMI

Smoking versus age, tumor location, and the number of cigarettes smoked:

Table 5: Distribution of the study subjects by gender and Smoking

Age/Gender	Male	Female	Total
Never	0 (0.00)	22 (12.08)	22 (12.08)
Former	5 (2.74)	29 (15.93)	34 (18.68)
Current	32 (17.58)	12 (6.59)	44 (24.17)
Ever	73 (40.10)	9 (4.94)	82 (45.05)
Total	110	72	182
p-value	0.0165	0.2459 ^{ns}	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.9835	-0.7541	

The distribution was according to the never, former, current, and ever. It was observed that 45.05% of 182 subjects are under ever smoking, among the men (110), 40.10% were smoking habits ever. As shown in fig 4.8b, there was a correlation between the men and smoking trend at p 0.0165 and no significant correlation in women according to Pearson r correlation.

Figure 6: Distribution of the study subjects by gender and Smoking

Table 6: Distribution of the study subjects by the duration of smoking and Location of tumor (n=160)

Duration	Right Colon	Left Colon	Rectum	Recto Sigmoid	Hepatic flexure	Total
≤20 yrs	16 (10.00)	9 (5.62)	4 (2.50)	3 (1.87)	0 (0.00)	32 (20.0)
20-30 yrs	42 (26.25)	23 (14.37)	7 (4.37)	1 (0.62)	3 (1.87)	76 (47.5)
≥ 31 yrs	16 (10)	19 (11.87)	12 (7.5)	4 (2.5)	1 (0.62)	52 (32.5)
Total	74 (46.25)	51 (31.87)	23 (14.37)	8 (5%)	4 (2.5)	160 (100)
*p-value	0.3000 ^{ns}	0.1878 ^{ns}	0.7913 ^{ns}	0.5122 ^{ns}	0.0877 ^{ns}	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.8910	0.9568	0.3220	-0.6934	0.9905	

Among the 160 subjects, 20% are having smoking habit ≤20 yrs, 47.5% are at 20-30yrs, and 32.5% are at ≥ 31 yrs. The study revealed that 46.25% are at right colon cancer and among 26.25% are having 20-30 years of smoking habit. There was no strong and significant correlation between the duration of smoking and tumor location in the selected subjects.

Figure 7: Distribution of the study subjects by the duration of smoking and Location of tumor (n=160)

Cigarette smoking is associated with increased incidence and mortality from CRC.

Cigarette smoking is also a risk factor for virtually all types of colon polyps. The association with smoking habits is greater in men with a strong correlation in all habits. Among the 182 subjects, 20.88% are with right-sided colon and the correlation is also high with smoking and also related to the duration of smoking. Among the patients, there are more smokers aged 20-30 years, and 26.25% have right-sided colon cancer, and the frequency of smoking is also related to the manifestation of the tumor. ≥ 20 smoking habits were observed to be more prone to 36.87% CRC and right-sided CRC was found more common in 46.25%. There was no strong correlation between smoking duration and smoking frequency with CRC.

Age VS Alcoholic Habits and Frequency of Alcoholism:

Table 7: Distribution of the study subjects by gender and Alcohol Consumption

Gender	Male	Female	Total
None	12 (10.90)	42 (58.33)	54 (29.66)
Beer	22 (20.00)	24 (33.33)	46 (25.27)
Wine	12 (10.90)	4 (5.55)	16 (8.79)
Liquor	64 (58.18)	2 (2.77)	66 (36.26)
Total	110 (100)	72 (100)	182 (100)
*p-value	0.3243 ^{ns}	0.7575 ^{ns}	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.6757	0.2425	

Table 8 summarized the distribution by gender and alcohol consumption and it was observed that among the subjects, liquor consumption was at 36.36%, wine at 8.79%, and beer at 25.27% and none of the above was at 29.66 . But in women (72) subjects the highest subjects are at none i.e 58.33% and among men (110) are more at liquor consumption (58.18). But overall consideration ,there was no significant correlation between alcohol consumption and CRC incidence in men (p 0.3243) and women (p 0.7575).

Figure 8: Distribution of the study subjects by gender and Alcohol Consumption

It was observed that out of 110 subjects, 58.18% have alcoholic habits and the rest drink wine, and beer, and none among the subjects with alcohol dependence, 36.26% are male (4,12). Regular habits with 15-21 units/week of alcoholism are 48.33% among 182 subjects. CRC of the right colon was found to be 23.33% in 87 subjects (4,13). According to previous studies, a positive correlation between alcoholism and tumor location has been reported. But in this study, there was a correlation only with right and left colon cancers and not with others.

Age versus tumor differentiation & Age versus histological grade:

Table 8: Distribution of the study subjects by Age and tumor differentiation

Age	Well-differentiated	Moderately differentiated	Poorly differentiated	Total
20-30	2 (2.5)	3 (4.47)	3 (8.57)	8
31-40	3 (3.75)	9 (13.43)	6 (17.14)	18
41-50	20 (25)	14 (20.89)	7 (20.0)	41
51-60	33 (41.25)	25 (37.31)	14 (40.0)	72
61- 70	13 (16.25)	12 (17.91)	2 (5.71)	27
71-80	6 (7.5)	4 (5.97)	3 (8.57)	13
>80	3 (3.75)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3
Total	80 (100) 43.95	67 (100) 36.81	35 (100) 19.23	182 (100)
*p-value	0.0001***	<0.0001****	0.0032**	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.9796	0.9838	0.9209	

Table 4.16 summarized the distribution of study subjects by age and tumor differentiation. In the present study population, 43.95% are with well differentiated, 36.81% are moderately differentiated and 19.23% are with poorly differentiated tumours at all age groups. The incidence was found to be more at 51-60years compared to other age groups. The incidence of 41.25% well differentiated, 37.31% moderately differentiated and 40% poorly differentiated tumours are at 51-60 years (72). It was observed that a strong correlation existed between age and tumor differentiation with pp-value of 0.0001*** for Well differentiated, <0.0001**** for Moderately differentiated and 0.0032** for poorly differentiated tumours.

Figure 9 Distribution of the study subjects by Age and tumor differentiation

Table 9 Distribution of the study subjects by Age and Histology grades

Age	Adenocarcinoma	Mucinous	Singet ring cell carcinoma	Sqamous cell carcinoma	Others	Total
20-30	6 (5.77)	2 (5.56)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	8
31-40	9 (5.65)	4 (11.11)	3 (13.64)	2 (18.18)	0 (0.00)	18
41-50	23 (22.12)	9 (25.00)	6 (27.27)	1 (9.09)	2 (22.22)	41
51-60	39 (37.50)	13 (33.33)	9 (40.91)	8 (72.73)	4 (44.44)	72
61-70	17 (16.35)	6 (16.67)	1 (4.55)	0 (0.00)	3 (33.33)	27
71-80	8 (7.69)	2 (5.56)	3 (13.64)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	13
>80	2 (1.92)	1 (2.78)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	3
Total	104	36	22	11	9	182
%	57.14	19.78	12.08	6.04	4.94	100
*p-value	<0.0001****	0.0001***	0.0030**	0.0106*	0.0076**	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.9968	0.9796	0.9233	0.8716	0.8878	

Table 9 summarized the distribution of study subjects by age and with the grading of histology. There was 57.14% of Adenocarcinoma; 19.78% of 19.78; 12. Signet ring cell carcinoma; 6.04% Sqamous cell carcinoma and 4.94% with other categories of CRC. All the types of histology grades were found to be more at the age of 51-60 yrs in the selected subjects. At the age of 51-60 years, it was observed that 37.50% of 104 subjects with Adenocarcinoma was the highest incidence of CRC. There was a strong correlation between the age and histology grade and $p < 0.0001$ is the more significant correlation compared to other grades of histology.

Figure 10 Distribution of the study subjects by Age and Histology grades

Differentiation is the grade of cancer based on how abnormal the cells look under the microscope. In well-differentiated adenocarcinoma, >95% of the tumor is made up of glands. Moderately differentiated adenocarcinoma shows 50-95% gland formation. Among 182 subjects, 43.95% were found to have well-differentiated cancers aged 51-60 years. At the age of 51-60, all types of well-differentiated, moderately, and poorly differentiated cancers are suspected. Younger patients with colorectal cancer have poorer differentiation.

In this study, it was observed that 57.14% of adenocarcinoma and 37.50% of adenomas are aged 51-60 years and there is a strong correlation between age and type of histological grade.

Polyp size thresholds of 6 and 10 mm are of particular importance. In this study, 36.81% of polyps 11-20 mm in size were more adenomatous.

Age vs Cancer Stage:

Table 10: Distribution of the study subjects by Age and stage of cancer

Age/Years	Stage 0-1 n (%)	Stage 2-3 n (%)	Stage 3-4 n (%)	Stage 4 n (%)	Total n (%)
20-30	3 (15)	3 (5)	2 (2.35)	0 (0.00)	8
31-40	2 (10)	9 (15)	6 (7.06)	1 (5.88)	18
41-50	3 (15)	10 (16.67)	24 (28.24)	4 (23.53)	41
51-60	8 (40)	26 (43.33)	32 (37.65)	6 (37.29)	72
61- 70	3 (15)	8 (13.33)	13 (15.29)	3 (17.65)	27
71-80	1 (5)	4 (6.67)	6 (7.06)	2 (11.76)	13
>80	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	2 (2.35)	1 (5.88)	3
Total	17 (100)	60 (100)	85 (100)	17 (100)	182
%	9.34	32.96	46.70	9.34	100
*p-value	0.0042**	0.0004***	0.0001***	0.0011**	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.9124	0.9667	0.9783	0.9498	

Table 9 summarized the distribution of subjects by age and stage of cancer. The stages are divided into 4 stages. It was observed that 9.34% are at Stage 0-1, 32.96% at stage 2-3, 46.70% at stage 3-4 and 9.34% at stage 4. The incidence was more at 51-60 years compared to remaining age groups and the distribution was as followed 40% of stage 1 subjects (17), 43.33% of stage 2-3 (60), 37.65% of stage 3-4 (85) and 37.29% of stage 4 (17) subjects. It was observed that a strong correlation is observed between the age and stage of cancer significantly at all stages.

Figure 11: Distribution of the study subjects by Age and stage of cancer

In this study, 46.70% are in stage 2-3 and 32.96% are in stage 3-4 and it was observed that subjects aged 51-60 years are in the advanced stage and younger are in stage 0-1 and advanced stages are over 60 years of age. The results of the study indicate that the correlation between age and stage of cancer observed the Pearson correlation between them.

Stage versus treatment:

Table 11: Distribution of the study subjects by Age and treatment option

Age	Surgery	Chemotherapy	Surgery + Chemo	Surgery+ Radio	Surgery+ Chemo+Radio	Total
20-30	4 (14.81)	3 (8.57)	1 (1.54)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	8
31-40	8 (29.63)	4 (11.43)	5 (7.69)	1 (2.70)	0 (0.00)	18
41-50	4 (14.81)	11 (31.43)	21 (32.31)	4 (10.81)	1 (5.56)	41
51-60	8 (29.63)	10 (28.57)	20 (30.77)	22 (59.46)	12 (66.67)	72
61-70	1	6	12	5	3	27

	(3.70)	(17.41)	(18.46)	(13.51)	(16.67)	
71-80	2 (7.41)	1 (2.86)	6 (9.23)	2 (5.41)	2 (11.11)	13
>80	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	3 (8.11)	0 (0.00)	3
Total	27 (100)	35 (100)	65 (100)	37 (100)	18 (100)	182 (100)
	14.83	19.23	35.71	20.32	9.82	
p-value	0.1681 ^{ns}	0.0100	0.0056* *	0.0061**	0.0091**	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.5846	0.8743	0.9011	0.8977	0.8791	

Table 11 summarized the relationship between the age and treatment modalities. The surgery (14.83%), Chemo (19.23%), Surgery+ Chemo (35.71%), Surgery+ Radio (20.32%) and Surgery+ Chemo+Radio (9.82%) was observed among the 182 subjects. The surgery was found to be more at 51-60yrs: 29.63% in 27, surgery+ radio: 59.46% in 65 subjects and Surgery+ Chemo+Radio:66.67in 18 subjects. But the modality chemotherapy was more at 41-50yrs (31.43%) and Surgery+ Chemo also at 41-50yrs (32.31%). The correlation was observed significantly in treatment modalities except surgery.

Figure 12: Distribution of the study subjects by Age and treatment modalities

Table 12 Distribution of the study subjects by Age and chemotherapeutic agents

Age/Therapy	Capecitabine	FOLFOX	CapeOx	FOLFIRI	Total
20-30	4 (16)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4
31-40	7 (28)	2 (3.70)	0 (0)	0 (0)	9
41-50	9 (36)	17 (31.48)	5 (18.51)	2 (16.66)	33
51-60	3 (12)	21 (38.88)	14 (51.85)	4 (33.33)	42
61-70	2 (8)	10 (18.51)	6 (22.22)	3 (25)	21
71-80	0 (0)	4 (7.40)	2 (7.40)	3 (25)	9
>80	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0
Total	25 (21.18)	54 (45.76)	27 (22.88)	12 (10.16)	118 (100)
*p-value	0.3988 ^{ns}	<0.0001****	0.0037**	0.0488*	Pearson r correlation
r value	0.3812	0.9938	0.9162	0.7571	

FOLFOX (5-FU, leucovorin, and oxaliplatin) or **CapeOx** (capecitabine and oxaliplatin)

FOLFIRI: leucovorin, 5-FU, and irinotecan (Camptosar)

Table 12 summarized the distribution of study subjects by age and chemotherapeutic agents. The usage of FOLFOX was found to be superior at 45.76% than Capecitabine, CapeOx and FOLFIRI. At the same time the application of Capecitabine (25) was found to be 36% more at 41-50yrs, FOLFOX (54) at 38.88% of 51-60yrs;CapeOx (27) was more at 51-60yrs with 51.85% and finally FOLFIRI (12) with 33.33% at 51-60yrs. There was a strong correlation between age and chemotherapeutic agents significantly at Pearson r correlation.

Figure 13 Distribution of the study subjects by Age and chemotherapeutic agents

In colon cancer, stage 0 is used to describe cancer that is in the inner lining of the colon but has not spread beyond it. Cancer at this stage is also called carcinoma in situ. In the current research, 35.71% of subjects underwent Surgery+ Chemo; 20.32% under surgery + radio; 19.23% under chemotherapy. In all treatment modalities, as mentioned, the age group of 51-60 years is compared to others. Therapy is purely dependent on the stage of colorectal cancer, according to age, 29.63% (27) are found with surgery at 31-40 years and 51-60 years; 31.43% (35) with chemotherapy aged 41-50; 32.31% (65) with Surgery+ Chemo aged 41-50; 59.46% (37) with Surgery+ radio aged 51-60; 66.67% (18) with Surgery+ Chemo+Radio. A strong correlation was found between age and all treatment modalities except surgery.

Colon cancer treatment by stage:

In other cases where cancer has metastasized and entered the lymph nodes, chemotherapy is necessary to help increase the patient's life expectancy. Medications may include oxaliplatin, irinotecan, leucovorin, UFT, capecitabine, or 5-fluorouracil. Monoclonal antibodies against molecular targets include cetuximab, panitumumab, or bevacizumab.

Although studies have claimed that first-line single-drug therapy is non-inferior to combination regimens in terms of overall survival (OS) (Seymour, M.T., 2007). combined therapeutic regimens of FOLFOX (5-FU+OX), FOXFIRI (5-FU+IRI), XELOX or CAPOX (CAP+OX), and CAPIRI (CAP+OX) remain the main approaches in first-line treatment.

In this study, only 118 patients are in the chemotherapy and adjuvant chemotherapy section as per their CRC stage. Among 118 subjects, 54% are under the FOLFOX regimen and, 22.88% are with the CapeOx regimen and, 33.33% are under FOLFIRI. Users under these therapies are aged 51-60 years for FOLFOX, CApeOx, and FOLFIRI. The Capcitabine treatment is found to be higher in 41-50 years.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The incidence of CRC was found to be more in men at 51-60 years of age. There was a strong correlation between age and gender distribution at a p-value of 0.0001. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. The number of subjects registered every year was found to be more with the elderly. The current study reported the same that, The age range of 51-60 was found more compared to other age groups in all years 2019-20; 2020-21, and 2021-22. There was a significant correlation between the age and year of registration at all the years at 0.0001 p-values. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. Our data shows that men have a comparatively higher risk of developing colorectal cancer than women and were more after 6-10 years of CRC. But there was no correlation existed between the first time of diagnosis and age distribution according to Pearson r correlation. The null hypothesis was accepted. Some researchers reported that an association exists between the age and BMI of the CRC subjects. A strong correlation is there between gender and BMI at p 0.0005 in men and p 0.0018 in women in this study and the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. Physical activity is also one of the factors for the CRC survivors, but observed that there was no significant correlation between gender and employment status; the null hypothesis was accepted. Among the 110 population of male patients with right colon was found to be more i.e prominent and there was a strong correlation between the gender and site of tumor presentation at p <0.0001. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. Age also influences the site of tumor presentation. The age of 51-60 yr was shown the highest percentage of CRC in all the tumor presentations in are

right colon. There was a strong correlation between the age and size of tumor presentation at p -value >0.005 . The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. The distribution was according to the never, former, current, and ever. There was a correlation between the men and smoking trend at p 0.0165 according to Pearson r correlation. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. The correlation was found to be more at the right colon in every smoking habit at p 0.0071 and rectosigmoid at 0.0146. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. The study revealed that right colon cancer and having 20-30 years of smoking habit are more. There was no strong and significant correlation between the duration of smoking and tumor location in the selected subjects. There was no significant correlation between smoking frequency with the tumor location. The null hypothesis was accepted. There was no significant correlation between alcohol consumption and CRC at $p > 0.05$. The null hypothesis was accepted. Among the population, more subjects are at (15.21 units consumed) right colon CRC. There was a significant correlation between units of alcohol consumption and tumor location only at the right colon and at the left colon. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. Among the selected subjects red meat and tea/coffee consumption was found to be more compared to others. There was a strong correlation between food consumption in the right colon, left colon, and hepatic flexure. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. There was a relation between comorbidities and the location of the tumor. It was observed that there was a strong correlation between the location of the tumor and co-morbidity for cardiovascular, diabetes, IBD, Peptic ulcer, respiratory issues, obesity, and arthritis. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. The distribution of study subjects by age and tumor differentiations like well differentiated, moderately differentiated, and poorly differentiated tumors at all age groups. The incidence was found to be more at 51-60 years compared to other age groups. It was observed that a strange correlation existed between age and tumor differentiation with a p -value >0.05 . The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. All the types of histology grades were found to be more at the age of 51-60 yrs in the selected subjects. There was a strong correlation between age and histology grade and $p < 0.0001$ is the more significant correlation compared to other grades of histology. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. The distribution was done by polyp size and type of tumor. The poly size was categorized as < 5 mm, 6-10mm, 11-20mm, and >20 mm. There was a correlation between polyp size and tumor type in dysplasia and adenocarcinoma. The null

hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. The distribution of subjects by age and stage of cancer. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. The modality of chemotherapy was more at 41-50 years and Surgery+ Chemo also at 41-50 years. The correlation was observed significantly in treatment modalities except for surgery. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. There was a strong correlation between age and chemotherapeutic agents significantly at Pearson r correlation. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. Distribution of selected subjects by age and Ostomy. The Ostomy was there more at 51-60 years. There was a correlation between age and Ostomy at $p < 0.0001^{***}$ for the Ostomy present and $p 0.01^*$ for the absence of Ostomy. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved. The correlation existed significantly between gender and type of Ostomy. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative was conserved.

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